

NICKNAMES AND LINGUISTIC TRANSFER IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *As in other languages, the transfer is considered one of the important evidences in Uzbek language, as well. In modern linguistics, metaphors are not only studied as a stylistic figure, but also they are an active member of nominative act, a piece of verbal thought of the language and is noted as a tool creating the linguistic picture of the world. This article studies the evidence of transfer in nicknames that have specific characteristics in the anthroponymic system of the language. In addition, the analyses of the active use of metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, simile, and irony as a linguistic-artistic tool in the formation of nicknames and epithets that are rich in stylistic color, connotative meaning, and other presuppositional meanings, are described.*

Key words: *transformation, stylistic tropes, metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, simile, irony, nicknames, zoonym-nicknames, ornithonym-nicknames, mythonomic nicknames.*

Nicknames have a special place in the anthroponymic system of the language and due to several lexical-semantic characteristics that they have, they encounter different semantic changes during the process of the linguistic communication. As other anthroponyms, nicknames and titles are also revealed in the form of words and word combinations. This phenomenon, *imprimis*, is observed in the example of the nicknames formed at the result of linguistic transfers. It is known that one of the phenomena laying under the nicknames, pseudonyms and epithets is the linguistic transfer. A metaphor, metonymy and synecdoche are used actively as a linguistic-artistic tool in the formation of nicknames and epithets that are rich in stylistic colour, connotative meaning and other presuppositional meaning.

A metaphor and nickname. In modern linguistics, metaphors are not only studied as a stylistic figure, but also they are an active member of nominative act, a piece of verbal thought of the language and is noted as a tool creating the linguistic picture of the world. If it is taken into account that metaphor is the result of human's cognitive act and is a speech component actively used in the speech process, "in a modern cognitive science, a metaphor is seen as a basis of such psychic processes as explaining, estimating, receiving and recognizing. A human does not only

express own ideas with the help of metaphor, but also thinks with metaphor, learns the world where he lives with the help of them. Metaphors help to change the linguistic picture of the world existing in the conscience of the receiver, to perceive the well-known phenomena with new categories. In this, the aesthetic potential of the metaphor, the ability to evaluate the existence emotionally plays an important role" [1:156].

There is a special linguo-cultural side of using the metaphoric lexicon as a nickname while describing the appearance and characteristic features of the person. In particular, while expressing his appearance and spiritual-mental, physical signs characteristic to him by zoonyms, phytonyms, astronoms, mythonyms, parts of the human body, objects (names (clothing, headdress, etc.) the breadth of the possibilities of the language are revealed. We once again witness that the language always creates a new meaning or a specific language sign from linguistic units and tools that already exist in it (the heterogeneity of the language).

Metaphor is mostly related to: 1) parts of human body (*hands, legs, face, lips, teeth, shoulders*); 2) clothing and any parts of it (*collar, hems*); 3) any parts of animals, birds or insects (*wings, tail, beak, horn*); 4) plant and its part (*root, vein, branch, leaf*); 5) weapons (*spear, knife*). For example: *Our village is in the hug of the mountain, In the hug of the mountain, On the side of the mountain, At the foot of it is a small stream, Clear in summer, clear in autumn, And the spring is all mud.* (Mirtemir) *Our house is in the collar of the river.* According to Z.R.Salimova, who specially studied this phenomenon in the example of Turkish language, there is a main stereotypical core of the knowledge repeating during the process of socialization of a person in a certain society. Therefore, certain stereotypes of describing a person is formed and sometimes, these stereotypical names are considered inappropriate to the culture. According to the scientists, stereotypes may be expressed in different linguistic forms, they are the lexico-semantic variations of the word, correlation with other words, its symbolic service and others. It is important to note about the transfer of the zoonyms into the people's names or nicknames that each level is aimed at understanding the qualities and personality of a person, characterized by an absolute selectivity in their metaphorical interpretation. [2:247].

1. **Zoonym-nicknames.** According to "Wikipedia", in Uzbek language the zoonyms consist of 564 articles, and 200 of them are actively used in the linguistic communication besides the scientific style [3]. The zoonyms used as nicknames for people are included in the list of those actively-used animal names, and in this case also, selectivity (choice) is evident, often the name of the animals that evoke a negative association in a person is transferred into a nickname: Mavlyan *the boar* Sabir *the dog*,

Karim *the pig*, Obid *the donkey*, uncle *Camel*, Tayir *the colt*, Murtaza *the cat*...

2. **Ornithonym-nicknames.** In the nicknames derived from the names of birds, they are nicknamed according to their height, structure, singing tone and way of living: Talib *the stork*, Zebi *the jay*, Samad *the sparrow*, Egam *the goldcrest*, Kamil *the quail*... Sometimes, the people with a beautiful voice may be given such nicknames like nightingale, parrot, tomtit as a compliment, and they carry positive meaning: Sherali *the nightingale**, Gulsanam *the parrot*, Bayram *the lark*...

3. **Mythonomic nicknames.** Mythonyms are the names of fictional objects, which are the transfer of names of characters from myths and legends [4:114] or popular works of art, movies and cartoons belonging to current mass culture into the nicknames: Batir the Giant, Yakshabek Khizr, Inayat Azrail, Sabir the Jinn (Karcha), Sheramat the Grandfather, Dilbar the Fairy, Davlat Saint; Ikram Robinson, Husan King Kong, Mickey Mehriban, Osman Terminator...

4. **Chrematonymous nicknames.** The transfer of the names of the material objects into the individuals: Azim machine gun, Sadriddin pistol, Akram pharmacy, Tilov stove, Ilkhom diamond, Kasim pipe...

A metonymy and nickname. The meaning arising from the connection of objects and events in space and time by transferring the name of one into the other is called metonymy. With this method, the similarity of external and internal signs is not taken into account in the transfer of meaning and form, but the existence of a constant connection between them comes to the fore. This situation is also evident in metonymic nicknames: Nayim *Effendi* (a reference to a punster person), *Schumacher* Tugal (a reference to the speed of a driver), *Pele* Hasan (a reference to a person's ability to play football well), *Ilkhom* samovar (a person who does not come from the cafeteria early or late).

A synecdoche and nickname. Synecdoche is a transfer of the meanings of the words based on the representation of a part by the name of the whole or, conversely, the whole by the name of a part. An example of this is somatism-nicknames. The linguistic and cultural background of such nicknames is related to the fact that some parts of a person are unusual and are distinguished from others in this respect. Yorkin *fangs*, Sarvar *teethy* (abnormal teeth), Ortikboy *big ear*, Razik *ear* (abnormal ears), Ghaibulla *big head* (too big head), Khumkalla, Jingalaksoch - *curly-haired* Alisher, Adil skeleton (referring to thinness), Tashkul *lung* (has a deficiency of breath). In this transfer the other change of the meaning is

* The component in a famous Uzbek folk singer Ergash Jumanbulbul's surname –bulbul (-ningale) was a nickname-epithet given to his father by the people. There existed a tradition of naming the people with a beautiful voice and speech after the birds that sing beautifully.

evident, in particular, the nickname *ear* is not only an abnormality in the ear, but also a sign of the person who bears this nickname, the ability to gossip. This state of meaning transformation can be defined as **synecdoche**.

Sometimes among the people, some nicknames given in a metaphorical way are ironically expressed in the language of the subject, without directly assessing the defects in the character and behavior of people. In particular, Shodmon "*mind*" - for his stupidity, recklessness; Rashid "*Khotamtoy*" - for his stingy, miserliness, meanness; Zoyir "*right*" - because of his injustice, *crooked hand*, that is, he is a theft; nickname "*sheryurak*" (lionheart) - for cowardice. In general, expressing the nicknames in an **ironical** way serves to increase the emotional-expressive colour.

The direct correlation of nicknames with the transfers shows that they occupy a specific place in the system of lexical units, in particular, of the onomastyc units. This is because that any nickname is formed as an artistic-descriptive tool as they are a secondary nominative tool. This is especially observed in the language of artistic works. Nicknames used in artistic and colloquial styles have a stronger emotion compared to nicknames in other styles (in journalistic, scientific and official styles there are also cultured nicknames). Therefore, the writer's goal is to create a brighter impression in the reader's mind and thereby he makes his hero remain in the reader's memory forever. The following examples from the artistic work can serve as a proof of our opinion:

"Bo'tqa, bo'tka, bo'tga, butga..."

He tried to pronounce the same word in different ways, but he still didn't like the tone. He thought that it was ugly, very ugly, it was also difficult to translate the rest. Porridge, that was semolina porridge... He did not know the meaning of the word "semolina" and was confused for a while.

Daroz and Khumkalla (*Yakhshibaev didn't want to call them with their names*), an essayist and a critic, were sitting at a table far away, looking forward to some of Yakhshibaev's gestures, reluctantly he spoke to them:...[5;166].

The only candidate is Olloyor. Good luck, Olloyor!.. laugh, play, be happy, Olloyor!! Don't be in a hurry, Olloyor, take your time, don't you hurry either, Comrade Yakhshibaev, after all, who called Olloyor a foaled colt, wasn't it you, Comrade Yakhshibaev. Maybe the colt will survive, but what will be the fate of the inheritance? [5;341].

Later, the sadness subsided a little. Yakhshiboy shepherd drops his staff, and a bit of heat penetrates his body, and he falls to the side of his flock. Mother also begins to live with hope. Especially when one year later, one of the two "black letters" (a letter from the war informing of a soldier's

death) taken turned out to be false, and their middle son came back fine. Kobil returnseda little more nervous - his head was shaking, his face was pale. After a year or two, he married to the girl who had become an old woman waiting for a groom, had children, and even when his head-shake disappeared, his nickname "**Kobil Kantujin**" (Kobil with a shaking head) remained. [5;413].

Yoshulli was an angry man. It was unforgivable that Yakhshibaev was jealous of Oshno and gave himself the nickname "**gorilla**". Then he could not forget that he read out a long list of illiterate leaders in a large meeting. Yoshulli's name was at the top of the list [5;535].

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